

ANOVA model. Each genotype was scored for 40 molecular markers single and multiple regression was used to estimate the proportion of phenotypic variation. Genetic variation explained by markers was estimated by dividing the phenotypic R^2 by the broad-sense heritability of each trait.

Broad-sense heritability of traits ranged from 0.81 to 0.37. Negative genetic correlations were found between most measures of fertility and vegetative persistence. Single QTL explained up to 27% of the phenotypic variation in the traits examined (see table). Multiple regressions explained from 7 to 38% of the phenotypic and from 18 to 62% of the genotypic variation in each trait. Some QTL appear to explain significant proportions of variation in several traits, suggesting pleiotropic effects. Marker G1184Ca is apparently linked to a QTL controlling the proportion of tillers that flower while having a negative pleiotropic effect on vegetative persistence. If this QTL is confirmed in further studies, it will represent a genetic locus that underlies the life history trade-off between reproduction and survival.

Our results contrast with recent QTL studies which have found chromosomal regions controlling large fractions of the phenotypic variation. We found only one case in which more

Single and multiple regressions of markers on traits. Underlined traits are those for which the annual ecotype expresses larger values (see references in Morishima et al 1992, Oxford Surv. Evol. Biol. 8:135-184).

Trait	Marker	Chromosome	$R^2_p^a$	$R^2_g^b$
Heading date	G1184Ca	1	0.135	0.175
	G1082	10	0.068	0.089
	Multiple regression		0.180	0.234
Anther length	RZ58	2	0.108	0.133
	G200	6	0.105	0.129
	G127	10	0.085	0.105
	G181	11	0.080	0.099
	Multiple regression		0.383	0.473
Height	C86	1	0.091	0.168
	G1184Ca	1	0.097	0.179
	C342	6	0.079	0.146
	G56	8	0.071	0.131
	Multiple regression		0.255	0.472
<u>Panicles tiller⁻¹</u>	G1184Ca	1	0.271	0.553
	RZ58	2	0.142	0.290
	Multiple regression		0.304	0.620
Panicle length	G1184Ca	1	0.062	0.124
	C196	2	0.118	0.235
	G1085	9	0.078	0.156
	Multiple regression		0.246	0.492
Spikelets panicle ⁻¹	G56	8	0.060	0.110
	C596	7	0.062	0.114
	Multiple regression		0.102	0.189
Regeneration index	G1082	10	0.066	0.179
Postharvest tillers/ preharvest tillers	G1184Ca	1	0.086	0.210
	C86	1	0.064	0.156
	C397	9	0.070	0.170
	C196	2	0.087	0.212
	Multiple regression		0.253	0.616
<u>Postharvest panicles/ postharvest tillers</u>	G1184Ca	1	0.168	0.271

^a R^2_p = phenotypic R^2 . ^b R^2_g = genotypic R^2 , calculated as $R^2_p \times H^2$.

than 25% of the phenotypic variation in a trait is explained by a single marker. Ecological adjustments that contribute to intraspecific annual \times perennial dif-

ferentiation in *O. rufipogon*, therefore, may be more polygenic than species differences examined in previous studies. ■

Determination of chromosome numbers of wild *Oryza* species conserved in the International Rice Genebank at IRRI

Bao-Rong Lu, Ma. E. B. Naredo, M. Macatangay and Ma. T. Alvarez, IRRI

To date, more than 3,000 wild rice accessions, representing 21 species of *Oryza* and 11 related genera, are being conserved in the International Rice Genebank (IRG) at IRRI. The chromosome number of each conserved accession of different *Oryza* species, which should be part of the passport data, is essential to facilitate characterization and species identification.

Number of accessions in each *Oryza* species for which chromosome number has been determined.

Species	Accessions (no.)	Chromosome number	Source
<i>O. australiensis</i>	17	24	Australia
<i>O. barthii</i>	141	24	Africa
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	11	24	Africa
<i>O. eichingeri</i> (diploid)	14	24	Africa, Asia
<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	37	24	South America
<i>O. granulata</i>	18	24	Asia
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	4	24	Africa
<i>O. meridionalis</i>	35	24	Australia
<i>O. nivara</i>	215	24	Asia
<i>O. officinalis</i> (diploid)	136	24	Asia
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	31	24	Asia
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	1	24	Indonesia
<i>O. alta</i>	6	48	South America
<i>O. eichingeri</i> (tetraploid)	4	48	Uganda, Sri Lanka
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	9	48	South America
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	5	48	Indonesia, Papua New Guinea
<i>O. minuta</i>	48	48	Philippines
<i>O. officinalis</i> (tetraploid)	2	48	India
<i>O. punctata</i> (tetraploid)	1	48	Kenya
<i>O. ridleii</i>	7	48	Southeast Asia
Total	742		

We have been observing chromosome preparations of root tips and pollen mother cells to determine the chromosome number of IRG wild rice accessions. To date, 742 accessions representing 18 wild *Oryza* species have been cytologically examined. Our observations (see table) revealed that, in general, chromosome numbers in the wild *Oryza* species were constantly $2n=2x=24$ in the diploid species *O. australiensis*, *O. barthii*, *O. brachyantha*, *O. glumaepatula*, *O. granulata*, *O. longistaminata*, *O. meridionalis*, *O. nivara*, *O. rufipogon*, *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*, and in the majority of *O. eichingeri* and *O. officinalis* accessions. They were

$2n=4x=48$ in the tetraploid species *O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, *O. longiglumis*, *O. minuta*, *O. punctata*, and *O. ridleyi*. Unexpected chromosome numbers were observed in *O. officinalis* and *O. eichingeri*. In a total of 138 *O. officinalis* accessions, 136 were found to be diploid ($2n=24$), but two accessions from India were tetraploid ($2n=48$). Our examination also showed that four accessions (out of 18) originally identified as *O. eichingeri*, from Uganda and Sri Lanka, had 48 chromosomes in the root-tip cells. Considering that both *O. officinalis* and *O. eichingeri* should be purely diploid species, the correct iden-

tification of the $4x$ forms must be confirmed. On the other hand, this observation also indicated the possible existence of two different cytological types of *O. officinalis* and *O. eichingeri*.

In addition, a low frequency of aneuploid cells with chromosome numbers varying between 20 and 26 were found in a few accessions of *O. australiensis*, *O. barthii*, *O. brachyantha*, *O. glumaepatula*, *O. granulata*, *O. meridionalis*, *O. nivara*, and diploid *O. officinalis*. A low number of tetraploid cells with 48 chromosomes was also observed in two *O. nivara* accessions and six *O. officinalis* accessions. ■

Genetics

Genetics of protein per grain in rice

S. Geetha and A. Ayyamperumal, Sugarcane Research Station, Sirugamani 639115, Tamil Nadu, India

Seed protein content is usually expressed as percent brown (dehulled) rice protein (BRP). This trait is highly influenced by environment and, hence, its expression is complex. It has been suggested that instead of considering BRP, it would be effective to use as selection criterion the actual protein

Analysis of variance for combining ability. Tamil Nadu, India. 1993 DS.

Source	df	Mean squares	F
GCA	5	0.71**	61.89
SCA	15	0.08**	7.38
Reciprocal	15	0.24**	20.70
Error	70	0.01	0.001
σ^2g	0.06		
σ^2s	0.07		
σ^2A	0.12		
σ^2D	0.07		
Predictability ratio			

$$\frac{2\sigma^2g}{2\sigma^2g + \sigma^2s} = 0.63$$

σ^2g = genetic component due to GCA

σ^2s = genetic component due to SCA

σ^2A = additive variance ($2\sigma^2g$)

σ^2D = dominance variance (σ^2s)

available per grain (PPG) since the latter is less influenced by environment. However, information on inheritance patterns of PPG in rice is scanty.

We studied gene action and estimated general combining ability (GCA) using six parents (IR50, ADT37, ADT41, Duansan, TKM6, and ADT39) and 30 hybrids generated through full diallel mating.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during the 1993 dry season. Each genotype (parents and hybrids) was planted in three rows of 3 m length and in 30 × 20-cm spacing in a field fertilized with 120 kg N ha⁻¹, 26.4 kg P ha⁻¹, and 49.8 kg K ha⁻¹. Observations were recorded for five randomly selected plants per replication.

A total of 100 fully filled, healthy grains from each plant were randomly sorted out and their weights recorded. Ten grains were taken randomly, dehulled manually, and ground to fine powder. Each sample was analyzed by the standard micro-Kjeldahl method to obtain %N. The BRP content was derived by multiplying %N by 5.95. The PPG (mg) was estimated as [%BRP × 100-grain weight (g) × 10].

The analysis of variance for GCA clearly indicated the importance of

both additive and nonadditive genetic variance (see table). The higher values (>0.5) of predictability ratios also revealed the preponderance of additive genetic variance. The additive genetic variance could be effectively used by simple pedigree method of breeding.

Among the six parents, IR50, ADT37, and ADT41 were found to be the best, and they could be used in hybridization programs to improve PPG. ■

The relationship between the morphological fertility of pollen and marker gene *Est 9*

Lu Chuangen, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanjing 210014, China; K. Takabatake and H. Ikehashi, Faculty of Agriculture, Kyoto University, Kyoto 606-01, Japan

Many indica-japonica hybrids exhibit a low seed set. In cases where female gamete fertility is normal, the lowered seed set can be attributed to pollen sterility. To use the strong heterosis of indica-japonica hybrids, we must overcome the barrier of pollen sterility.

We analyzed genes for pollen hybrid sterility in F₂ populations from three-way crosses of Akihikari //IR36/